

In Search for Service Quality: The need for the Digitization of Printed Library Resources by the Colleges of Education in Nigeria

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Abstract

Keywords: Academic libraries, Service quality, Digitization, Printed library resources, Colleges of Education

Introduction: Many library patrons in Nigeria, particularly students in academic library environments, are digital natives who are better attuned to digital resources and services due to their convenience for access and use. The digitization of printed library resources in the Colleges of Education (COE) libraries in Nigeria would lead to higher efficiency and effectiveness in library operations, resulting in better service delivery and greater user satisfaction.

Methodology: This article employs a desk research approach to explore service quality in academic library environments, focusing specifically on the need for digitizing printed library resources by COEs in Nigeria.

Findings: The concept of service quality is examined, and its dimensions are highlighted. The practices of service quality in libraries are discussed, and digitization is presented as a pathway to achieving service quality in libraries. The benefits of digitization in libraries are also highlighted.

Conclusion/Recommendations: The paper recommends that COE libraries should keep pace with digital advancements to maintain relevance in the 21st-century society. Other recommendations include ensuring that digitization efforts are aligned with the goal of enhancing service quality and user satisfaction.

Introduction

In Nigeria, Colleges of Education (COEs) are a strata of the higher educational setting that are saddled with the responsibility of training individuals that are interested in having the minimum required benchmark for teaching at the nursery, primary and junior secondary school level. Their mandate is to develop a crop of the required competent talent that is required to lay the foundation for a

sustainable knowledge economy, especially because the development of education from the lower level of education is a major component of national development. According to Oladumijoye (2013), the first teachers training college in Nigeria was established in 1896 (St. Andrews College, Oyo), followed by several others in 1897, 1904, 1905, 1928 and so on, in different parts of the country.

Like every other library at the higher education level, libraries at the COEs are classified as academic libraries. In other words, academic libraries are information/knowledge banks that are rooted in the universities, polytechnics, research institutes, colleges, and other post-secondary institutions of learning that harvest, process, and provide quality information products and services to their students, faculty, and researchers to enhance teaching, learning and research activities (Usman and El-Kalash, 2024). The aim of academic libraries is to acquire, organize, preserve, and disseminate timely, relevant and trustworthy information products that are customized to the mission/objectives of establishing their parent bodies. In other words, the priority of academic libraries is to generate, organize and provide documented knowledge to their parent organizations.

In a bid to offer a better explanation of the concept of academic libraries, the American Library Association (2022) stated thus:

“Academic libraries work together with other members of their institutional communities to participate in, support, and achieve the educational mission of their institutions by teaching the core competencies of information literacy—the abilities involved in identifying an information need, accessing needed information, evaluating, managing, and applying information, and understanding the legal, social, and ethical aspects of information use”.

Nonetheless, academic libraries have much invaluable impact on scholarship and the general well-being of society. Though, the issue of the quality of services they render to their users comes into question especially as the expectations of contemporary academic library practices are not merely tied to the availability and currency of the information resources that are available in them, but also, the ease at which such information resources are accessed and the customer relations activities they offer. In other words, the metrics for understanding the effectiveness and efficiency of the services that academic libraries offer have shifted significantly from the much-placed value on the available collections in them, to that of visibility and ease of access. That is why the quality of an academic library has shifted from what the library houses, to the available information products and services that the library users can access. Hence, the necessity of this paper especially because academic libraries of the present century have to key into the trends that the emerging community of users prefer to utilize.

Understanding Service Quality

Historically, scholars have regarded the concept of service quality as being particularly challenging to define and quantify especially because of the intangible character of services and the fact that they are sometimes subjectively experienced. However, evaluating service quality as a management tool has been increasingly important in most service companies during the last few decades, particularly in libraries and information centers (Association of Research Libraries, 2018). Service quality is said to entail the overall assessment of how well a service meets or exceeds customer expectations. In other words, it is a measure of the extent to which a service fulfills customer needs and requirements.

The Indeed website (2022) defined service quality as a measure of how an organization

delivers its services compared to the expectations of its customers. Similarly, Parasuraman, et al. (1985) as cited by Sarmah and Singh (2021) averred that service quality measures how well a product or service meets a customer's expectations, while Bitner and Hubbert (1994) defined service quality as the customer's overall impression of the relative inferiority/superiority of the organization and its services. Below are some fundamental beliefs that underpin the concept of service quality as outlined by Sarmah and Singh (2021):

- a. Measuring the quality of service is more complex than measuring the quality of a product.
- b. The customer's view of service quality is crucial.
- c. Service quality refers to the difference between the service's outcome and the customer's expectations before the service.

Since the main objective of every library is to satisfy the demands of its patrons, and its priority is to offer the appropriate information material at the appropriate time, in the appropriate place, and at the appropriate cost, the issue of service quality becomes important. This is because; service quality increases the productivity of libraries and boosts their reputation. By implication, offering high-quality service is essential to luring and keeping library customers, especially in this information age.

Dimensions of Service Quality

Many organizations have different metrics for measuring their service quality standards. Hence, service quality varies by brand promise. For example, a secondary school library user has a limited expectation on service quality standards, compared to that of a university library user. Despite these variations, (Klokkenga, 2020) stated that there is a popular and standard way to measure service quality and SERVQUAL, which was coined by Zeithaml, Parasuraman,

and Berry has regularly been used based on a set of five factors, being the most crucial for service quality in every industry. Further, (Klokkenga, 2020), citing Zeithaml, Parasuraman and Berry offered the following as the five service quality dimensions:

- a. **Tangibility:** This is the appearance of physical facilities, equipment, personnel, and communication materials. Customers tend to expect clean and professional facilities and shops, employees who look groomed and neat, and well-written and designed materials such as menus, websites, and signs. Attention to appearance can indicate that your company takes customer comfort seriously. While appearance is not the most critical aspect of service, it does make a difference in how customers perceive your business, especially if your brand promises a premium or luxury experience.
- b. **Reliability:** This is the ability to perform the promised service dependably and accurately. Doing what you say you're going to do when you say you're going to do it is essential to pleasing your customers. They want to rely on your business to deliver a working product or effective service, to get help when they need it, and for all of this to happen in a timely fashion. Customers want to count on the businesses they buy from - that's at the heart of this dimension.
- c. **Responsiveness:** Responsiveness is the willingness to help customers and provide prompt service. Responding quickly to customer questions and concerns is vital, especially in today's fast-paced world. Responsiveness even applies when customers are slow in responding to you. Answer swiftly to, at the very least, let customers know that you're working on their

request. Responsiveness lets your customers know that you're listening to them and working actively to solve their problems.

- d. **Assurance:** It is the knowledge and courtesy of employees and their ability to convey trust and confidence. Customers expect businesses to be the experts in the service they deliver. Communicating that expertise to customers helps reassure them that they can trust you, whether you accomplish this by displaying credentials and industry certifications or customer testimonials. Assurance is significant when customers have many options but aren't sure who to trust when purchasing. Suppose you run an e-commerce store, for example. In that case, customers are bombarded regularly with ads from potentially untrustworthy online shops all day, so you need to determine how to set yourself apart and gain consumer trust.
- e. **Empathy:** It implies the caring, individualized attention the firm provides its customers. Customers want to feel like they're more than a transaction; they want to build a relationship with your business. Even if you have the best product or services on the market, you can still fall short of their expectations. Showing empathy to customers' means ensuring your company showcases your care. Training employees on how to provide excellent and empathetic service—where smiles and engaging conversation occur regularly—can help you exceed expectations.

Service Quality and Libraries

In contemporary library environments, service quality entails the overall evaluation of how well the libraries meet the needs and expectations of their users in terms of the services they offer. Said differently, library service quality encompasses various aspects that directly impact the user experience within the library environment. Some key elements of service quality in contemporary libraries entail the provision of:

- a. **Access to Resources:** Libraries are expected to provide easy and convenient access to their entire resources such as books, journals, databases, multimedia materials, and digital content. More so, the issue of access includes ensuring that the collection is comprehensive, up-to-date, and relevant to the users' needs.
- b. **Assistance and Support:** This implies ensuring that the libraries have knowledgeable and helpful staff that can assist users in finding the resources they need. Also, it includes the provision of guidance on research methodologies, and offering technical support on how to use library systems and equipment.
- c. **Facilities and Environment:** The library should provide a comfortable and conducive physical environment for studying and research. This includes factors such as adequate seating, well-organized shelves, quiet study areas, computer workstations, and amenities like photocopying and printing services.
- d. **Information Literacy and Instruction:** This has to do with the provision of programs and resources that would enhance users' information literacy skills. Such programs include workshops, tutorials, and training

sessions on effective research techniques, citation management, and utilizing library resources effectively.

- e. **Timeliness and Efficiency:** Library services should be delivered promptly and efficiently. This is achieved through fast and accurate retrieval of materials, quick response times to user queries, and efficient circulation processes for borrowing and returning items.
- f. **User Engagement and Outreach:** Libraries are expected to actively engage with users and their communities, organize events, workshops, and exhibitions, as well as seek feedback that would continuously improve services, based on user needs and preferences.
- g. **Technology and Digital Services:** In modern library environments, providing access to online databases, digital collections, e-books, and other electronic resources is very essential for the attainment of quality service provision. That is why the library's website and online catalogue is usually emphasized to be user-friendly and intuitive, to facilitate easy search and resource discovery.

By focusing on the above aspects of service quality, libraries strive to ensure that their users have a positive and enriching experience, can easily access the information they require, and receive the necessary support to make the most of the library's resources and services.

Digitization: A Pathway to Attaining Service Quality in Libraries

Digitization is an activity that centers on converting analogue information into digital form. It is a process that involves the conversion of physical objects or data, such as

books, documents, images, audio recordings, and videos, into a digital representation that can be stored, manipulated, and accessed electronically. The practice is a paradigm shift that has significantly improved library and information science (LIS) practice across the globe. Hence, any library that wants to maintain relevance and successfully compete in the information services industry of the present society has to dive headfirst into the digitization space.

Several scholars and authors have defined the concept of digitization using different standpoints. For instance, The National Library of Australia (cited in Etim, Ebong and Gilead, 2012) defined digitization as a process of creating digital surrogates (versions) of analogue materials from the library's collection. Further to the definition, the library outlined the following as the activity cycle for digitization: capturing, storage, management and long-term preservation and most importantly disseminating this digitized information in the libraries for the information society. In the view of Bandi, Angadi and Shivarama (2015), digitization is a shorthand phrase that describes the process of making an electronic version of a 'real world' object or event, enabling the item to be stored, displayed and manipulated on a computer and disseminated over networks and/ or the World Wide Web. Further, they stated that such images may be captured using a scanner or digital camera while OCR software may be employed for the electronic image to optimize clarity, while El-Kalash (2019) conceives digitization as a process of preserving information items through selection, acquisition, preparation and data capturing of documents, sounds or images via any electronic device that is capable of capturing texts, sounds or images, for onward storage, access and transmission into a digital platform.

From the above definitions, digitizing an item means trying to have a digital representation or a copy of that thing that you wish to digitize

to be in a digital form because the process of digitization does not involve replacing an original document, image, sound, etc. in its entirety (El-Kalash, 2019).

Benefits of Digitization in Libraries

Digitization of library resources offers several benefits that revolutionize access to information and enhance preservation efforts. In the view of Musa (2012), providing access to digitized collections can help publicize the materials to other departments and peers in other institutions around the world, thereby demonstrating the importance of the collections. Further, the author argued that digitizing information resources in academic libraries raises the profile of the library and the institution to the top ranks of institutional repositories. The digitization of priceless and valuable collections of the institution brings prestige to the whole institution as it creates visibility not only of the library's (institutions) content, but the scholars work within the higher institution of learning (Musa, 2012).

For Pandey and Misra (2014), digitization of library resources implies that a large number of library users can access a single material at the same time. The authors noted that this also saves time and goes in line with Ranganathan's fourth law of library science which emphasizes on saving the time of the reader, while Otubelu and Ume (2015) summarized the benefits of digitizing library resources as access, support of preservation activities, collection development, institutional and strategic benefits, research and education. Further, the authors emphasized that digital materials can be made available to a broader audience than those who have the resources or ability to travel to see the analogue collections, and access can be expanded to non – traditional audiences such as lifelong learners.

More so, digitization expands the availability of resources through the sharing of digitized collections among libraries. This promotes collaboration and enriches the diversity of materials accessible to researchers and learners. Also, digitization brings about time and cost efficiencies by eliminating the need for physical reproduction and distribution of materials. It also supports remote learning and research, as users can access digital collections anytime and anywhere.

However, Dhule (2018) in an article titled: Digitization of libraries: benefits and challenges highlighted the following as the benefits of digitization of library resources:

- a. The benefit of digitization is improved access. Digital libraries are typically accessed through the Internet and Compact Disc-Read Only Memory (CD-ROM). They can be accessed virtually from anywhere and at any time. They are not tied to the physical location and operating hours of the traditional library.
- b. A digital library can provide wider access, and meet simultaneous access requests for a document by easily creating multiple instances or copies of the requested document. It can also meet the requirements of a larger population of users easily.
- c. Improved information sharing. Through the appropriate metadata and information exchange protocols, digital libraries can easily share information with other similar digital libraries and provide enhanced access to users.
- d. Improved preservation. Since electronic documents are not prone to physical wear and tear, their exact copies can easily be made. Thus digital libraries facilitate the preservation of special and rare documents and artifacts by providing access to digital versions of these entities.

- e. Digital materials can be available to a broader audience than those who have the resources or ability to travel to see the analogue documents and access can be expanded to non-traditional audiences such as lifelong learners.
- f. Digitization of libraries will help to preserve endangered library resources, improve the efficiency of information search mechanisms and enhance access to library resources.

Nonetheless, digitization of library materials has many benefits as it transforms accessibility, preservation, and collaboration amongst others in the digital age.

The Issue of Digitization by the Colleges of Education Libraries in Nigeria

There is no gainsaying the fact that the Colleges of Education in Nigeria play a vital role in shaping the future of the nation's education system. As centers of teaching and learning, they strongly rely on the information resources in their libraries to support the academic and professional development of students and faculty. Though, these libraries have placed much reliance on printed library resources that pose challenges in terms of accessibility, preservation, and service quality because at the time of writing this paper, no public college of education in the country is, out of the 81 colleges, fully engaged in digitization activities.

While we cannot risk shelving aside the fact that the printed library resources have long been the foundation and backbone of knowledge repositories in our institutions of learning, contemporary realities highlight that physical books and journals present limitations such as limited availability, restricted access, and the risk of damage or loss amongst others. These limitations of printed information materials make it difficult to satisfy the information needs of 21st-century library users especially because they are digital natives. In other words, while the printed information resources in our COE

libraries often present limitations that hinder quality service delivery to students and faculty in terms of accessibility, preservation, and user experience, digitized information materials have a greater capacity to enhance service quality. Hence, the need for the digitization of printed library resources has become increasingly apparent, especially in the face of a rapidly advancing digital era. By embracing digitization, the COEs can provide a seamless and enhanced learning experience to their users.

Quite interestingly, the degree of comfort usually experienced by library users who utilize digitized materials encourages independent learning. More so, when the printed library materials are digitized, they are preserved and conserved. By implication, physical handling and exposure to damaging environmental conditions would be reduced, and the longevity and availability of those valuable resources for future generations to utilize, thereby safeguarding our cultural heritage would be ensured.

Nonetheless, it is unarguable that the COEs in Nigeria must recognize the pressing need to digitize their printed library resources. By so doing, the quality of their services would be enhanced especially because the benefits of digitization, including improved accessibility, preservation, search capabilities, and collaboration, cannot be ignored. By embracing digitization, the public COEs in Nigeria can empower their students and faculty with a rich and diverse digital collection, ensuring a high standard of service quality. Only then can the Nigerian COEs truly unlock the transformative potential of digitization and provide their stakeholders with exceptional learning and research experience.

Conclusion

The digitization of printed library resources has emerged as a transformative trend in academic libraries, significantly impacting service quality. By improving accessibility,

preserving valuable materials, enabling advanced search and discovery, and promoting collaboration, digitization is an activity that enhances the overall user experience in contemporary academic library environments. Hence, academic libraries in Nigeria must embrace digitization and address the associated challenges to leverage their full potential in providing high-quality services to their users.

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